

CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03- Data availability and File Format explained

Where to find the CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03 data files:

The CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03 data are available from the BADC Archive at:

<http://badc.nerc.ac.uk/browse/badc/cru/data/crutem/crutem4/CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03>

CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03 Data File Format explained:

The CRUTEM4.2.0.0-2013-03 data are stored in both ASCII and NetCDF formats:

ASCII data

All values are stored as temperature anomalies in degrees Celsius;

Missing data are set to the value given in the header. (normally $-1.0e-30$).

Grids are 5x5deg monthly.

The day (irrelevant here), month and year are stored at the start of each month.

Field status flags indicate whether the field is finalised ("f") or preliminary ("p").

- Finalised fields are fixed and will not be updated under the current version number.
- Preliminary fields may be updated in future monthly updates if additional data becomes available.

Data Array (72x36)

Item (1,1) stores the value for the 5-deg-area centred at 177.5W and 87.5N

Item (72,36) stores the value for the 5-deg-area centred at 177.5E and 87.5S

NetCDF data:

Missing values are indicated within the files.

Please see the CEDA NetCDF pages at <http://www.ceda.ac.uk/help/users-guide/file-formats/netcdf/> for more information on how to read NetCDF data.